

RESEARCH AND CALCULATION OF THE ZONE OF CONFIDENT SIGNAL RECEPTION OF DIGITAL SOUND RADIO BROADCASTING TRANSMITTER'S SIGNAL

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ABSTRACT

The article examines current trends in the development of digital radio broadcasting, including the transition from analog to digital signals, the development of standards and their application in various countries. Special attention is paid to the relevance of research and calculation of digital broadcasting coverage areas, which is crucial for optimizing infrastructure, uniform access to information and ensuring high-quality services. Examples of successful implementation of digital radio broadcasting technologies in developed countries, including Norway, Great Britain, Germany, and Switzerland, are given. A generalized algorithm for calculating the safe reception zone of a digital audio broadcasting transmitter is proposed.

Digital radio broadcasting is a modern technology for transmitting radio signals based on digital information processing, providing higher sound quality, the ability to transmit related data and efficient use of the radio frequency spectrum. Digital radio broadcasting is developing in various formats and standards, depending on the region, technologies and solutions used.

Before the advent of digital radio broadcasting, the basis of the radio industry in the 20th century was analog radio broadcasting, represented by the AM (amplitude modulation) and FM (frequency modulation) formats.

By the end of the last century, its shortcomings became apparent.:

- limited sound quality (especially in the AM band).
- high exposure to noise and interference (atmospheric, industrial, from electrical appliances).
- inefficient use of the radio frequency spectrum (each program occupies a separate frequency band).
- limited possibilities for transmitting additional information (text, images, and metadata).

Digital technologies at the end of the last century provided new opportunities for radio broadcasting, allowing to eliminate these limitations [1-3].

The transition to digital broadcasting is based on the following key technological concepts:

1) Digital signal processing. A digital signal is a discrete sequence of data encoded as binary bits. This allows you to apply noise reduction and error correction algorithms, encode audio using lossless compression methods (for example, AAC, MPEG).

2). Multiplexing (OFDM). Orthogonal Frequency multiplexing (OFDM) allows multiple data streams to be transmitted in a single frequency band. This solves the problem of the limited frequency spectrum.

3). Modulation and demodulation. Digital radio broadcasting uses more stable modulation methods such as QPSK or 16-QAM. These methods increase resistance to noise, which significantly affects analog signals.

4) Compared to the analog signal, the digital signal has the following advantages:

- Improved sound quality. In the FM band, digital radio broadcasting provides high quality audio, eliminating distortion and noise. In the AM band, the digital signal eliminates the crackling characteristic of analog systems.

- Efficiency of using the frequency spectrum. A single digital frequency (multiplex) can transmit up to 12 channels, unlike a single program in analog format.

5) Additional functions and data. The digital signal allows you to transmit: song titles and artists, program grids (EPGs), interactive content (in hybrid systems).

6) Energy efficiency. Digital transmitters consume several times less energy than analog transmitters, which reduces operating costs.

At the same time, there are some problems of the transition period to digital broadcasting:

- the need to replace or upgrade receivers;
- limited coverage area at the initial stage;
- high cost of equipment.

Digital radio broadcasting continues to actively develop around the world, providing listeners with improved sound quality and additional services (Fig.1).

Norway. It became the first country to fully switch to digital radio broadcasting in the DAB+ format in 2017. This has improved the sound

quality and expanded the number of available radio stations [4-6].

Great Britain. It is actively developing digital radio broadcasting, and by the end of 2024, most radio listeners prefer digital platforms. The country plans to completely abandon analog FM broadcasting in the coming years.

Germany. DAB+ coverage has significantly expanded, and by the end of 2024, most households have access to digital radio. It is planned to further develop the infrastructure and gradually abandon analog broadcasting.

Switzerland. Completed the transition to digital radio broadcasting in 2024, disabling analog FM transmitters. This has ensured better and more stable radio broadcasting throughout the country.

In Uzbekistan, digital radio broadcasting is currently in the planning and testing stages. Projects for the development of telecommunications infrastructure and digital technologies are being implemented in the country, which creates the prerequisites for the successful implementation of DAB+ digital radio broadcasting in the near future.

The development of digital broadcasting standards has become a key stage in the transition from analog to digital broadcasting. Different countries and regions have chosen their approaches to creating standards based on technical, economic and geographical conditions [6-9].

Fig.1. Status and development of digital radio broadcasting (end of 2024)

The main standards developed so far include DAB/DAB+, HD Radio, DRM, ISDB-Tsb and others. Each standard has its own strengths, and their choice depends on the needs of a particular region, the available frequency spectrum, and economic factors.

DAB (Digital Audio Broadcasting) and DAB+ are one of the first digital broadcasting standards developed in Europe and approved in 1995.

The features of the DAB/DAB+ standard are:

- based on orthogonal frequency multiplexing (OFDM), which allows multiple programs to be transmitted in the same frequency band;
- The MPEG Layer II codec is used for audio compression (in DAB), and the improved version of DAB+ uses the more efficient AAC+ codec.;
- provides resistance to interference and the ability to transmit related information (text, images).

It is most actively used in European countries such as Great Britain, Germany, Norway, Switzerland, as well as in Australia.

HD Radio is a standard developed in the USA to ensure a smooth transition from analog to digital broadcasting.

The features of the HD Radio+ standard are:

- the "Hybrid Digital" method is used, which allows transmitting a digital signal simultaneously with an analog signal on the same frequency;
- Supports improved features: higher sound quality, stereo sound for AM stations, text information, etc.

It is most widely used in the USA, Canada and Mexico. The advantage of the standard is the ability to use the existing analog broadcasting infrastructure.

DRM (Digital Radio Mondiale) is a standard developed as a replacement for analog broadcasting in the AM and FM bands.

The features of the DRM standard are:

- Supports broadcasting in the short, medium and long wave bands (DRM30) and in the FM band (DRM+);
- High sound quality is provided even at long distances, which makes it especially attractive for use in countries with a vast territory.;
- allows you to transfer related information, such as text messages, electronic transmission programs (EPG) and maps.

It is actively used in India, Pakistan, and some African countries. It is an attractive choice for countries with low population density due to the low cost of covering large areas.

ISDB-Tsb (Integrated Services Digital Broadcasting - Terrestrial Sound Broadcasting) is a Japanese digital radio broadcasting standard developed on the basis of ISDB-T (television broadcasting) technology.

The features of the ISDB-Tsb standard are:

- provides digital audio integration with digital TV;
- supports mobile reception, which makes it popular in Japan.

It is mainly used in Japan, where ISDB standards are widely used for both television and radio broadcasting.

Table 1 shows a comparison of digital audio broadcasting standards [10-12].

Table 1

Comparison of digital broadcasting standards

Standard	Ranges used	Sound quality	Spectrum efficiency	Geographical application
DAB+	HF (Band III, L-Band)	High	High	Europe, Australia, South Africa
HD Radio	FM, AM	High	Average	USA, Canada, Mexico

DRM	AM, FM	High	High	India, Africa, South America
ISDB-Tsb	VHF, UHF	High	Average	Japan

Digital radio broadcasting is becoming the main direction of radio communications development. However, its effective implementation requires careful planning, especially in terms of coverage area.

The main problems are:

- uneven coverage of the territory, especially in rural and remote areas;
- the influence of terrain and dense urban development on signal quality;
- limitations of the frequency spectrum used for broadcasting;
- the need to minimize costs in the construction of infrastructure;

In these conditions, the study and calculation of the coverage area of digital broadcasting becomes a key task.

Therefore, the tasks of researching and calculating the coverage area of digital radio broadcasting are relevant for the following reasons:

1) Resource optimization issues. Accurate calculations of the coverage area make it possible to optimally place transmitting stations, minimizing equipment and operating costs. Effective use of the radio frequency spectrum requires understanding how the signal propagates in specific conditions (terrain, climate, building density).

2) Ensuring uniform access. To achieve equality in access to information, it is important to ensure coverage in both urban and rural areas. The presence of "white spots" in the coverage area reduces the quality of services and user trust.

3) Socio-economic importance. Radio broadcasting is an important channel for the dissemination of information, especially in

emergency situations. In rural and remote areas, digital radio broadcasting remains one of the main and accessible sources of information.

4) Impact on the quality of the service. Incorrect design of the coverage area can lead to interference, poor sound quality, and loss of listeners. Modern users expect high-quality sound and stable reception anywhere.

In order to conduct research and calculate the coverage area of digital audio broadcasting based on the DAB+ standard in relation to the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a generalized algorithm (Fig.2) and a specialized calculation program was developed [13, 14].

The generalized algorithm for calculating the zone of reliable reception of a digital radio transmitter signal, taking into account the terrain and climatic conditions, consists of 9 blocks and works as follows.

Block 1. This is where the initial data is prepared and entered for calculations.:

- terrain, using Open Street Map (OSM);
- climatic conditions (temperature, precipitation, clarity, etc.);
- parameters of the transmitter (RTS) (frequency f , antenna height h_1 , DAB+ mode, protection level, coordinates, real (S_{real}) and ideal (S_{ideal}) signal levels).

Block 2. The type of terrain on which the digital radio broadcasting transmitter is installed is selected. Possible options: city, suburb, rural area.

Block 3. Here, one of two possible calculation options is determined: with or without interference. When the case is selected, the transition to block 5 occurs without interference, otherwise to block 4.

Block 4. In this block, the value of the transmitter using factor Q is calculated.

Block 5. Here, the transmitter power values and the distance between the transmitters are calculated, as well as coverage area graphs for the without interference case.

6-block. Here, the parameters of the transmitter and the distance between the

transmitters are calculated, as well as coverage area graphs for the case of interference.

Block 8. The results of calculations and dependencies are displayed on the screen.

7-block. Is it necessary to display the calculation results on the screen? If "Yes", then there is a transition to block 8, otherwise to block 9.

Block 9. If it is necessary to repeat the study, then the transition to block 1 occurs, otherwise the calculation ends.

Fig.2. Generalized algorithm for calculating the zone of confident reception of the digital audio broadcasting transmitter signal

The calculating program is developed using the Python programming language and is designed

to calculate the zone of reliable reception of a digital radio signal, taking into account the terrain features and climatic factors [15, 16]. The Folium

library is used to display geospatial data and maps. The program implements a map style using Folium capabilities, which allows you to visualize elements such as river bends, coastal zones, shaded terrain areas (hills and mountains), as well as displaying natural vegetation and other natural objects. In fig.3. the program's appearance is shown (Fig.3, a) and examples of calculations of the secure reception area for the city (Fig.3, b), rural areas (Fig.3, c) and suburbs (Fig.3, d).

The features and advantages of the developed algorithm and program for calculating the coverage area of a digital audio radio transmitter are given. are the following:

- 1) Allows you to analyze the factors affecting signal propagation:
 - terrain (mountains, plains, etc.);
 - characteristics of the urban environment (high-rise buildings, dense buildings);

- climatic conditions (temperature, humidity, precipitation).
- frequencies used (for DAB/DAB+).

2) Modeling of the coverage area:

- application of mathematical models of radio wave propagation;
- using the developed software for calculations.

3) Optimizing the placement of transmitters:

- determination of antenna height and transmitter power;
- minimizing the overlap of signal zones from different transmitters (to prevent interference).

4) Conducting tests:

- comparison of calculated data with actual measurements;
- adjustment of calculation models if necessary.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig.3. Examples of calculating the zone of reliable reception of a digital radio signal, taking into account the terrain features and climatic factors

Based on the analysis and research, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. The transition from analog to digital broadcasting is a natural stage in the development of the radio industry, providing new opportunities for users and broadcasters. This is a complex process that requires investment, planning, and

coordination, but its benefits far exceed its costs, making digital radio the standard of the future.

2. Digital broadcasting is a step into the future that provides users with higher—quality audio, additional data, and flexibility in content consumption. The main drivers of development include technical innovation, support from national governments, and the growing popularity of mobile devices.

3. Calculating the coverage area of digital radio broadcasting is a multi—level process that allows for high-quality and uniform radio coverage. Taking into account technical and socio-economic aspects, such research contributes to the development of digital radio broadcasting, increasing the availability of information and optimizing infrastructure costs. Modern calculation and modeling methods make this process accurate, efficient, and vital for all countries transitioning to digital technologies.

4. A generalized algorithm and program for calculating the zone of reliable reception of a digital audio broadcasting transmitter signal have been developed, taking into account the terrain and climatic conditions.

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